

SITE GPR	YEAR 2012	AREA F	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: Max:	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 5146 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropogenic	
In cross-section? ☐ Yes ☒ No		In elevation drawing? ☐ Yes ☒ No		Photos: ☐ Yes ☐ No #: 2745-47	Photo Model: ☐ Yes ☒ No #:	
DEFINITION rubble wall south of B-house			Covered by ☒ SU: 0	Fills ☐ SU:	Filled by ☐ SU:	
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? ☐ Color ☐ Composition ☐ Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS ☐ Accumulation ☒ Construction ☐ Cutting ☐ Erosion ☐ Collapse ☐ Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (frequent, (m)edium, (r)are)			SOIL/MATRIX clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% ☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive			
Anthropic ☐ Pottery ☐ Tiles ☐ Amphorae ☐ Dolia ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☐ Mortar ☐ Coins ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Glass	Nails ☐ Marble ☐ Quarried debris ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Basalt slabs ☐ Opus signinum ☐ Painted plaster ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Other (specify)	Geological ☐ Tufo (specify) ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)	Organic ☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☐ Animal bones ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)	Compaction ☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft	Color ☐ Black ☐ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)	
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						
Northern Limit ☐ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit		Southern Limit ☐ Original ☐ Not Original ☒ Excavation Limit		Depth: ☐ Original ☒ Not Original		
Western Limit ☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit		Eastern Limit ☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit				
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE						
Is equal to:			Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abuted by:			Abuts:			
Is covered by:			Covers:			
Is cut by:			Cuts:			
Is filled by:			Fills:			
OBSERVATIONS wall was excavated previously by the Italian state archaeology and it's connection with our excavation got clearer in 2012						
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: south-eastern edge of trench F						
Shape: linear						
For layers complete this section: Surface (slope direction, visible inclusions): Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): Nature of the interface with layer below: ☐ sharp ☐ diffuse ☐ commingled ☐ other (specify):						
For cuts complete this section: Cut edges: ☐ rounded ☐ straight Cut sides: ☐ straight ☐ concave ☐ convex ☐ sloping Cut bottom: ☐ flat ☐ concave ☐ irregular How is cut top edge? ☐ sharp ☐ rounded How is cut bottom edge? ☐ sharp ☐ rounded Observations:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):			

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) Irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

greyish, difficult to judge since it has been restored by Italian workmen

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

*Ca. 13,5 m of wall within our excavation permit
 width: Ca. 1,50m, height: 0,91m*

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Retaining wall for a street, heavily restored and excavated without stratigraphical recording. Therefore it is difficult to assume it's original state.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by: *CMH*

Revised by: *CMH*

PDFd by:

Entered by:

on: *30.7.2012*

on: *1.9.2012*

on:

on: